

New European Bauhaus Academy

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Barcelona, February 27, 2026

Teaching NEB to students of architecture

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1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference
Knowledge, Skills, and Innovation in sustainable construction for a resilient future of Europe
Barcelona, February 27, 2026

The total number of trained and certified students by now:

Undergraduate (Bachelor) level:

Information Technology for Sustainable Design

- BIM with Elements of Algorithmics 3 ECTS / 50 students

Graduate (Master) level:

Urban Regeneration and Cultural Heritage Seminar 1 ECTS / 55 students

Urban Regeneration Project 6 ECTS / 64 students

**The courses certification was based on completed assignments and projects,
and NOT on a 'certificate of attendance' basis!**

Feedback was collected through the post-training evaluation surveys.

Information Technology for Sustainable Design
BIM with Elements of Algorithmics

NEBA pilot course: Information Technology for Sustainable Design - BIM

SINGLE-FAMILY HOUSE

DESIGNED IN A SUSTAINABLE MANNER

POLAND, ŁÓDŹ, JANA KIEPURY ST. 78/27

GROUND FLOOR PLAN SCALE 1:100

SECTION A-A SCALE 1:00

AXONOMETRICAL VIEW OF ROOF CONSTRUCTION

DETAIL B SCALE 1:10

HEAT LOSS THROUGH THE GROUND

HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENT TO THE GROUND						
Type of element	l	λ	α_e	R_{se}	R_{si}	U_{se}
H	H	[W/(m ² K)]	[1]	[m ² K/W]	[m ² K/W]	[W/m ² K]
ground floor	1,45	0,380	54,91	0,234	1	-1,689
						-1,5489

Type of thermal bridge	l	λ	α_e	R_{se}	R_{si}	U_{se}
CI	1,5	-0,05	1	-0,27		
Roof/ceiling	32,079	-0,05	1	-1,64815		
wall/floor	32,079	0,65	1	20,05805		
wall/window in the construction layer	2,2	0	1	0		
						18,274

HEAT LOSS DUE TO THERMAL BRIDGES IN CONNECTION OF BUILDING COMPONENTS LISTED ABOVE

DESCRIPTION

- THERMAL BRIDGE
- HEAT TRANSFER

DESCRIPTION

- THERMAL BRIDGE
- HEAT TRANSFER

"A HOUSE MAINLY MADE OUT OF WOOD GREEN ROOF AND RICH IN GREENERY ENVIRONMENT" 30% CREATIVITY

"MODERN HOUSE DESIGNED WITH CONCERN TO SUSTAINABILITY. SOLAR PANELS ON ROOFING. 0% CARBON DIOXIDE EMISSION" 30% CREATIVITY

AI VISUALISATIONS

NEBA pilot course: Information Technology for Sustainable Design - BIM

To better demonstrate the ideas of the New European Bauhaus through BIM, it's worth translating them into simple and visible design activities, such as clear models and visualizations. Showing real examples and using 3D visualizations will help everyone more easily to see how these ideas influence the appearance and quality of the spaces which we use every day. Integrating NEB principles into everyday BIM work and education makes them more understandable and easier to apply.

U VALUE

- Wall - 0,168 W/m2K
- Garage roof - 0,124 W/m2K
- Roof - 0,114 W/m2K
- Floor - 0,255 W/m2K

LOW-IMPACT DETACHED HOUSE

PROJECT PROVIDES A CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE BUILDING WITH USAGE OF RENEWABLE MATERIALS. CONTINUATION OF THERMAL INSULATION PROVIDES EXCELLENT THERMAL EFFICIENCY WHILE FITTING AESTHETICALLY WITH REST OF THE STRUCTURE.

SUSTAINABLE VARIANT 1

SUSTAINABLE VARIANT 2

FLOOR ANALYSIS

U VALUES TABLE

Element	U-value [m ² K/W]
Exterior wall	0.15
Exterior garage wall	0.18
Roof	0.12
Floor	0.10
Terrace slab	0.13

FOUNDATION SLAB ERADICATES THERMAL BRIDGES ON THE FLOOR WHILE TRIPLE GLAZED WINDOWS REDUCE UNNECESSARY HEAT LOSSES THROUGH WALLS. BALCONIES KEEP CONTINUITY OF INSULATION MAKING THE HOUSE EASILY MAINTAINED.

CROSS SECTION A-A 1:100

SOUTH ELEVATION 1:100

ROOF STRUCTURE

CROSS SECTION B-B 1:100

WEST ELEVATION 1:100

GROUND FLOOR 1:100

UPPER FLOOR 1:100

Lodz University of Technology

New European Bauhaus Academy

Circular Bio-based Europe

Joint Undertaking

NEBA pilot course: Information Technology for Sustainable Design - BIM

Bio-based Industries Consortium

Co-funded by the European Union

Urban Regeneration and Cultural Heritage Seminar

Seminar. Urban Regeneration and Cultural Heritage

CAROUSEL BRAINSTORM

- ANALIZA ISTNYCH BUDYNKÓW
- DIALOG MIĘDZY SPECJALISTAMI I ARCHYTEKTAMI
- WYKORZYSTANIE METODY BRAINSTORMINGU
- MODERNIZACJA ENERGETYCZNA BUDYNKÓW
- * * * * *
- WYKORZYSTYWANIE ŹRÓDEŁ ENERGII (ODNAWIALNEJ)
- ZARZĄDZANIE WODĄ I ZASOBAMI NAT.
- WYKORZYSTYWANIE MATERIAŁÓW O NISKIM ŚLADZIE WĘGLI, np. DRENO
- SYMULACJE ENERGETYCZNE
- ZNAJOMOŚĆ PRZEPISÓW I REGULACJI
- ANALIZA PRZESTRZENI
- WYKORZYSTANIE ZASOBÓW I MATERIAŁÓW
- ZWYKŁE PRACY I WYKORZYSTANIE WYKONCZONYCH PRAC

**New European Bauhaus Academy Course:
SEMINAR. URBAN REGENERATION AND CULTURAL HERITAGE**

Carousel Brainstorm

TOPIC 1.

Please indicate what knowledge and skills architects need to acquire in order to be able to apply sustainable solutions in adaptive reuse design tasks.

**New European Bauhaus Academy Course:
SEMINAR. URBAN REGENERATION AND CULTURAL HERITAGE**

Carousel Brainstorm

TOPIC 2.

Please indicate what changes are needed to make decarbonization and circularity as driving forces in urban regeneration.

**New European Bauhaus Academy Course:
SEMINAR. URBAN REGENERATION AND CULTURAL HERITAGE**

Carousel Brainstorm

TOPIC 3.

Please indicate which green technologies and bio-based solutions could be applied to the built heritage.

Conventional vs. Sustainable Building Systems in Revitalized Buildings: How to Design the Future?

The recycling of building materials in the context of the renovation of historical buildings

The impact of extreme temperatures on the revitalization of public spaces

THE ASPECT OF CLIMATE CRISIS IN THE PROCESS OF URBAN ENVIRONMENT REVITALIZATION

Revitalization or Displacement? The Double-Edged Sword of Urban Regeneration and Gentrification

URBAN REGENERATION OF PREFABRICATED HOUSING ESTATES IN POLAND

The New European Bauhaus: Prizes and Practical Design

Revitalisation in the Digital Era – BIM and Digital Twins as tools for preservation and revalorisation of historic buildings

**Spaces for People:
Adapting Industrial Heritage for Social Functions**

The image shows a woman with long dark hair and glasses sitting at a desk in a lecture hall, working on a laptop. Behind her is a large projection screen displaying a presentation slide. The slide is titled 'Verkatehdas Culture and Congress Centre' and 'Hämeenlinna, Finland, JKMM Architects'. It features a list of bullet points and several small images of the building and its surroundings. The woman is looking towards the screen, and the room is dimly lit, with the screen being the primary light source.

Verkatehdas Culture and Congress Centre
Hämeenlinna, Finland, JKMM Architects

- o 2002
- o Built on a site of a former textile factory
- o Urban and social issues due to the factory closing in the 1990s
- o Repurposing the site into a culture and arts centre
- o Sensitivity to context, materials and users
- o Culture, education and recreation
- o Combining old buildings with new structures
- o Integrating the community through shared experiences

Source: <https://jmm.fi/work/verkatehdas/> (Accessed 12.11.2025)

Aspect of Climate Crisis in the Process of Urban Environment Revitalization

ABSTRACT: Provided article is an attempt to verify methods counteracting the aspect of climate crisis which has a strong physical impact on the direction of contemporary architecture and particular guidelines followed in the process of urban revitalization. The main theme is to present the areas sensitive to the factors of urban adaptation which act for the benefit of counteracting the climate change by proposing technological solutions and certificates supporting an ecological approach to urban development.

INTRODUCTION

The global issue of climate crisis enforces inevitable challenges regarding the complex process of urban environment revitalization. In the face of uprising temperatures, air pollution and flood risk, revitalization must take into account specific technologies and solutions in order to counteract such phenomenon. These actions not only cover the architectural section in the urban context but also significantly influence the social aspects related to the quality of life, contributing further to the creation or restoration of more resilient and environmentally friendly urban spaces.

The unchanging tasks of revitalization include improving technical condition of buildings and infrastructure, reversing the process of social, economic and material degradation, preservation of urban values and monuments. Apart from the field of architecture, it also involves social and cultural activities which aim to improve the quality of life of residents by activating local communities and protection of cultural heritage.

A common element combining climate crisis and revitalization process is the bilateral share of influence on aspects concerning social and economic relations, interpersonal relations and the quality of life in urban space, which are highly dependent on factors. Urban revitalization

¹ Jaraczewski W. (2009) Przestrzenne aspekty rewitalizacji – środowiska, blokowiska, tereny poprzemysłowe, polodroże i powojkowe. 978-83-89440-51-8. (Tom 4). Kraków: Instytut Rozwoju Miast.
www.researchgate.net/publication/338363303_Przestrzenne_aspekty_rewitalizacji_rodzimisla_blokowiska_tereny_poprzemyslowe_polodroze_i_powojkowe_2018.

Revitalization as a Tool for Transforming Copenhagen into a Climate-Resilient City

ABSTRACT:

Green Roofs and Walls as Elements of Revitalization – The Impact of Green Wall and Roof Installations on Building Insulation and Air Quality Improvement.

ABSTRACT: Green roof and wall installations are innovative architectural solutions, designed to be a response to the current environmental and social challenges. The issues caused by urbanization and climate change can be minimized by the implementation of green technologies in new building investments, but more importantly in revitalization of the existing buildings and urban areas. This paper provides comprehensive analysis of the importance of green roofs and walls in revitalization processes set to improve urban living conditions. This essay describes systemic and technical solutions of green roofs and walls, and also lists challenges and future prospects in their implementation. It also includes case studies of the green solutions on the worldwide scale.

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is one of the most significant global trends of the 21st century, the exponential growth of the number of people living in cities has significant, and multi-layered impact on the world we live in. The issue of ongoing urbanization challenges current architects and urbanists worldwide but it is set to become a much more serious problem in the near future. In accordance to the data presented by the United Nations, approximately 55% of the human population currently live in urban areas. This proportion is set to increase to 68% expected by the year 2050. The global urbanization and continuous change in residence of the population from rural to urban areas, paired with the areas worldwide¹. The ongoing expansion of urban areas has resulted in a significant number of environmental challenges such as habitat loss, degradation of biodiversity, creation of urban heat island effect resulting in cities having much higher ambient temperatures than rural areas, increase in air pollution, and unsustainable energy consumption². The mentioned negative effects present in the urban areas are to a large extent caused by the unsustainable building and urban development. The usage of a variety of unsustainable, unecological, and toxic materials in building development contributes to the degradation of the environment, and act as a catalyst in the negative climat

¹ United Nations, 2018
² Zappere, Wayne C.; Northrop, Robert; Andrew, Michael. 2020. Urban Development and Environmental Degradation. Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Environmental Science. Oxford University Press

Buildings revitalization and reconstruction in the modern timber technology and its influence on the environment

ABSTRACT:

Biodiversity Protection in the Process of Revitalizing Degraded Areas

This paper addresses the protection of biodiversity in the revitalization of degraded areas, focusing on Nature-based Solutions (NBS)¹ and providing examples from cities such as Paris, Manila, and Singapore. It discusses ecological and social benefits, including improved quality of life for residents, social integration, and adaptation to climate change. The conclusions indicate that nature-based revitalization plays a key role in creating resilient and people-friendly cities.

INTRODUCTION

The revitalization of degraded areas plays a crucial role in counteracting the effects of urbanization and industrialization, which often lead to environmental degradation and biodiversity loss. This process not only restores the aesthetics of urban spaces but also supports ecological balance and improves living conditions for residents. In the context of climate change, Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are gaining increasing importance. Their objective is to integrate natural processes into the planning and management of urban spaces in a sustainable manner. NBS combine ecological, social, and economic aspects, offering benefits to both the environment and communities.

In light of challenges such as biodiversity loss and climate change, implementing solutions like ecological corridors, rain gardens, and microforests has become imperative. This paper examines the practical application of these solutions, presenting examples from various cities around the world and their impact on biodiversity protection and climate change adaptation.

NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS

Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) are an innovative approach that integrates natural processes and ecosystems into urban planning and space management in a sustainable way. NBS utilize the capabilities of ecosystems to address social, economic, and environmental issues, improving urban quality of life and enhancing biodiversity. According to the European Commission, NBS are actions

Recycling of building materials in the context of historical buildings renovation.

ABSTRACT: This study underlines the importance of integrating reused and recycled materials in the

The Impact of Green and Blue Infrastructure on the Urban Revitalization Process

ABSTRACT: The overall aim of the thesis is to present the regeneration process as a holistic reconstruction of cities to meet both social and environmental needs. By highlighting the positive impact of sustainable management of water resources and green spaces, it is hoped that the change in perception and appreciation of revitalised urban areas by their inhabitants will be highlighted.

INTRODUCTION

The term 'revitalization' is derived from the Latin words 're' and 'vita', which together mean 'bringing back to life'¹. In a general sense, this definition encompasses a series of interventions aimed at improving living conditions in social, economic and aesthetic terms.

In an architectural and an urban context, this term refers to the set of planning activities aimed at transforming degraded areas into safe and people-friendly spaces. These activities prioritise the needs of the local community. They also include the modernization of infrastructure and public spaces and the introduction of sustainable solutions in terms of green and water management. The latter, which involves the creation of green spaces and watercourses, is extremely important. The provision of such areas is essential for the proper functioning and well-being of residents. Therefore, in order for the urban landscape to evolve and strive for environmental stability, it is necessary to introduce a stable water and green economy into the revitalisation process.

CHALLENGES OF DEGRADED URBAN AREAS IN CONTEXT GREEN AND BLUE INFRASTRUCTURE

Local urban authorities are currently facing major challenges as a result of increasing urbanisation and the degradation of green spaces. These are related to dangerously rapid urban expansion and development and climate change. Chronic droughts are destroying soils, record summer temperatures are dangerously heating up city centres and causing fires, and prolonged and intense rainfall is causing flooding. Air and water pollution are also affecting human health and well-being.

The solution to problems that have been underestimated for years lies in a revitalisation programme. It consists of a series of interrelated measures to ensure a sustainable future for urban

¹ <https://pl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rewitalizacja> (Accessed: 19.11.2024)

POST-TRAINING EVALUATION SURVEY

(on-line anonymous questionnaire)

Likert scale questions:

1. Thanks to the training, I acquired new knowledge.
2. The training programme developed my professional skills.
3. I found the first part of the training, with its group work and debates, attractive and engaging.
4. The training met my expectations.
5. The aim of the training was clear.
6. Taking part in the training helped me to **understand the principles of sustainable development in adaptive reuse of existing buildings and regeneration of urban areas.**
7. The training enabled me to **understand the advantages and limitations of applying circular solutions to existing buildings and urban areas.**
8. During the training, I learned about the **challenges facing the architecture and construction sector in relation to reducing the carbon footprint.**
9. The training provided me with new knowledge that I can apply to my design work in adapting existing buildings and revitalising urban areas.

Scale 1-5, where 1 means "strongly disagree" and 5 means "strongly agree".

SATISFACTION RATE

POST-TRAINING EVALUATION SURVEY

(on-line anonymous questionnaire)

Open-ended questions

1. In what ways does your understanding of **the principles of the New European Bauhaus** influence your approach to architectural and urban design?
2. Is there anything you would like to change about the organisation of the training?
3. Which part of the training found most valuable? What did you learn from them?
4. How do you envisage the future of architectural and urban design in the context of the need to decarbonise the construction sector?

Ad 1:

*„I am very interested in the topics of **material reuse and circularity**, and I would like to incorporate them into my projects, whether in my professional work or my studies. I believe it is important to have an organisation like **NEB that promotes these principles.**”*

Ad 4:

*„If we introduce innovations and educate society, this future could become a reality sooner than we think. **Personally, I would like to see the construction sector decarbonise rapidly. As architects, we should be given the opportunity to learn how to use materials that support this process**, but some of our courses discourage us from looking for new solutions and we end up choosing traditional reinforced concrete structures.”*

Ad 3:

*„Presentations and discussions: sharing our thoughts and perceptions on specific topics. This allowed me to focus more on understanding the contemporary challenges faced by architects. **By architects, I mean not only creators of form, but also people who influence the quality of life and the sustainable built environment.**”*

Urban Regeneration Project

Thank you 😊

Anetta Kepczynska-Walczak

Bartosz Walczak

More on this topic in the article:

Kepczynska-Walczak, A. (2025). Implementing Sustainable Transformation in the Built Environment: Evaluation of the Experimental Phase of the New European Bauhaus Academy Alliance Pilot Project. *Sustainability*, 17(13), 5959. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17135959>

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